

Evaluation of the dental implant body on the stiffness, novel approached utilizing Mohammed bodies

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Abstract

These are generalized headlines to demonstrate the effect of the implant on the stiffness that will affect the bone ultimately

Keywords: Bone, Biomechanics, dental implants, ankylotic teeth, stiffness of bone, jaws weakeners, jaw stiffeners.

Passive vs active stiffness

Dental implants are metallic object that replace considerable part of the bone in the term of stiffness. The dental implant will affect the bone if they are directly involved in the stresses transfer or passively by just presenting inside of the bone. It is well known than the presence of a metallic heavy plate is capable of hindering the growth of the jaws if placed in the period of active growth. Nevertheless, even adults have continuous morphology changes that is sensed by many researchers. The effect on the stiffness is highly affected by the shape of the implant. More deformable implant means less stiffness equivocally. We had demonstrated this in our previous paper . Most of the changes in the bone is coming from the passive effect of the stiffness change due to the passive effect of the implants.

Displacement is the main criteria for stiffness evaluation

Fixation of the numerical models at the base is the best boundary condition which had not been reported in any previous paper previous according to the knowledge of the authors

This is the most advanced novel approach to evaluate the dental implant stiffness

Passive stiffness is related directly to the core of the implant

The effect of the passive stiffness on the growth is well known on the growing individual (1). It also affects the dental implants (2).

What is Mohammed bodies

We have assigned the modulus of elasticity of the bone block in all of our models as cancellous bone, a value close to what had been supposed in different FEA studies done by other authors. Even with this very soft material, we found that bone deformity is limited, and both threaded implant and only core implant had in many models close results. In many times we call the block as The bone Many technical obstacles had been faced during our works, but we had passed them.

In almost all studies of the finite element analysis in implant dentistry, there is no consensus and agreement about many variables, so we start depending upon our experience. Our current work project could be improved in the future. This book is very much like a seed for a tree. With someone has an idea, even it is not well organized or even without showing result, it is better to be written and recorded. Surly it needs some discussion with others to make it more mature.

In Histopathology studies, different stains give their histopathologists a clear idea about the disease or pathological changes. Multiple plots, as well give clear ideas about possible failure and could be anticipatory of the mode of failure.

The load is only the single player in the determination or guarantee succeed in implant design.

A text says about Per-Ingvar Brånemark that he was a bioengineer, whose in reality was an orthopedic surgeon The Swedish bioengineer Per-Ingvar Brånemark in 1952 was the first one who used the term osseointegration to describe the direct structural and functional connection between living bone and the surface of an implant.

Why we chose Ti grade 5? It widely accepted that as one of the best-used alloys for surgical devices, especially osteosynthesis plates. It had a great ration of strength/weight ratio with excellent corrosion resistance. We choose the implant with a diameter of 3.5mm and 4.5mm and a length of 10mm. We see this is the most used dimension in the main author surgical career. Before we start our work, we designed the virtual lab equipment. In our virtual lab equipment, which is a device that could control the applied forces and forces timings. Also, there is a special place for the fixture to be used for the only intended situations.

All of our CAD works could be in further future analysis or construct physical devices or equipment, for example, to validate our FEA results. High strength titanium alloy, 6Al4V, was used in all of our experiments. The head used as an attachment to the apartment to apply forces was parallelepiped as this will give us a better demonstration of any displacement or change that happening in the studied domains, and it is rigid and stiff enough to resist any possible deformity when the load is applied over it.

The connecting screw was held in position without any allowed movement with the implant, nevertheless, we believe that it could be modeled the same as the real model, but we want to demonstrate the major features of implant design rather than this feature. We assumed it as the same property of the implants as the 6AL4V was assigned for both of them. The material of the implant was the same as the abutment. In the ISO 14801 requirement of dynamic loading test for endosseous dental implants, no choice of implant less than 8 mm, and the maximum load is 499N, but this is an inclined application of the testing force and has Y and X components.

According to the Pythagoras' theorem, the vertical force should be about 282 newtons, but we choose 200newton because it is a number that could be easily dealt with. In orthopedic surgery, it is well established that stiffer design is accompanied by a stress shield. To detect the effects of bone and the implant configuration on the stiffness, we had been used in these conditions, for each design:

- Modular implants.
- Monoblock implants.
- Modular implant with united modules to investigate the effects of cutting material in case of modular design, and the implant stiffness is affected by the modularity is due to these hallowed spaces or due to the movement between parts.

When adding bone to the implant simulation, the variable will be more and the results interpolation will be more complex. To define and explore the native variable of the implant a naked implant had been simulated. In all designs, the same conditions had been assumed. First of all, choosing the main feature of the implant, the core. There are 2 core types:

- non-tapered thin core model
- tapered thin core model

Both had 2 varieties, threads or fins and plateaus.

We added thread to the implant or fins designs over these cores. Threads even have a more complex effect on implant performance than the fins, as they have continuity with each other in an inclined fashion. In many instances, we just test these cores to see if the core had the main effect on the performance or from the fins or threads.

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So, we take the core of threaded or finned implants (the cores of both are identical) to test it. In the case, we want to test the implant without investing medium or bone we chose to fix it from the base. The base of the implant where it is minimum and non-deformable non-moveable. These presented models may not give the full complete idea about dental implant performance, but it provides a parametric standardized approach to establish a method of dental implant evaluation that could be adopted in the future and for other designs as well. Even in other disciplines like orthopedic surgery or arthroplasties designs, this work is applicable. In this edition, we must emphasize that we want to establish a good start on a sound basis. - Establishing models that could fulfill the criteria to evaluate any future variable in dental implant design.

- Establishments a new methodology of implants evaluation. Many methods applied to limited models of designs could be applied to others in our bodies.
- Plots had been put with our best effort to tailor them to be suitable to highlight concepts of modern biomechanics. Their approach intended to be close to objectivity, nevertheless subjectivity could not be eliminated totally

p(1)=0

Contour: First principal strain (1) Contour: Third principal strain (1)

Figure 1344

It indicated that tension on the side of force application faced by compression on the opposing region on the contralateral side

The figure shows clearly the concentration of tension represented by the first principle strain at the side of force application and area of compression on the contralateral side of force application

This pattern of distribution we had called monolithic distribution

In the area A & B, due to concomitant occurring of the 3rd and 1st principal strain at the same time the dominant 1st at area B and 3rd at area A will get a more uniform pattern

While the other has it is in a vertical orientation to the dominant world has less uniformity

As the C and D are in the vicinity of the attached base there will be reciprocation in the site of strain above and below the line E

In the area of the hollowed region of the implant (area F) more mixing of strains occur

In the area G, as it is hollowed portion and have the least diameter compared to all regions of the implant more mixing and more significant occurrence of the pattern seen that region A and B

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The representation of these stresses within the implant is going in the same pattern of distribution like what happened in the case of third and first principal strain distribution

Both areas A and B had less as they are less involved in the deformation

Figure 1347

Second principal strain shows clearly the uniform symmetrical distribution of shearing within the implant

Those areas must be considered when designing composite implants and functionally graded implants, as the effect of shearing, compression, torsion... etc. have significantly different impact on the material that is used to construct the prosthetic device whether it is implantable or not

Implantable devices must have a more restricted rule for design and material selection

Figure 1348

The distribution of second principal stress have the same pattern of distribution on the strain but in different locations

Same as figure 4 but this figure show the effect of changing range of values that determine color distributions

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Displacement growth or pattern growth may be more important than the highest value in the final deformation.

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Figure 1352

Same

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Volume: Total displacement (m)

Figure 1353

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Slice: Stored energy density (N/m²)

Figure 1354

Growth of strain energy density

$p(1)=0$

Slice: Stored energy density (N/m²)

Figure 1355

Same

p(1)=0

Slice: Stored energy density (N/m²)

Figure 1356

Same

p(1)=0

Slice: Stored energy density (N/m²)

Figure 1357

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The distribution areas of stored energy density are the same on both sites and the fatigue will affect these regions, at the same time, more than other regions. These regions must be considered when

Figure 1359

Growth of von mises stresses

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Slice: von Mises stress (N/m²)

Figure 1360

Same

p(1)=0

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Figure 1361

Same

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growth of von mises stresses resemble the growth stored strain energy density

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Area A is much more widely and with wide gradient away from line c

The same in area d and E with line f

Figure 1364

Second principal strain distribution for the finned implant is the same as the thick monoblock and the base had been engaged in the strain within the thread strain also occurred

Neck had no significant difference from that of the thick monoblock.
In our studies, we tried to make the range of the legend universal for each criterion to make comparisons more intelligible

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The reduced amount of mass of the implant changed significantly distribution of first and third principal regions

regions of the fins tips have significantly less comparatively than those of regions in between them

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Same off thick model

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Bodies of fins closer to the base engaged in the energy density than those near the neck

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The base of fins engaged also in the stress

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We think that if Legend modified it would be revealed

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The first and third principal strain is the same as in the finned model, but as the base of the implant is close to the neck more deformity closer to the base will occur.
The radius of the neck is 1.25mm while radius at the base is 1.2383mm

Slice: Second principal strain (1) Slice: First principal strain (1) Slice: Third principal strain (1)

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Strain energy density in the neck region had nearly the same distribution in finned implant, threaded implant
Regions near the base significantly have greater involvement
And the fins near the base are fully engaged

Figure 1378

Same

Figure 1379

Same

Figure 1380

Featureless implant tapered no significantly different with the fins tapered, but the absence of a fence further reduce the mass of the implant

Slice: Third principal stress (N/m²) Slice: First principal stress (N/m²) Slice: Third principal stress (N/m²)

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This figure shows clearly first and third principal strain in the neck region and the region of the base have a heavier density

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Figure 1385

Same as finned tapered

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This design is an intermediate transition between the thick and tapered featureless design

Noticeable that the strain at the site of force application is higher in an implant with greater mass

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Figure 1390

Same

Figure 1391'

Same

Figure 1392

Same

Figure 1393

This is the growth of the displacement

Figure 1394

Same

Figure 1395

Same

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Same

Figure 1397

Same

Figure 1398

This is the growth of the strain energy density with progressive loading

Slice: Elastic strain energy density (N/m²)

Figure 1399

Same

Figure 1400

Comparing of the upper region with the lower region showing that the lower region grow much greater and faster than upper region indicating that which region will be responsible for the return of the implant after deloading at this level

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Same

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At this level of deformation, the upper region begin to deform more

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Figure 1410

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this could be due to error in the setting of the FEA in the package software

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Same as finned tapered

Figure 1417

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Figure 1418

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Presence of the last thread inclined could affect the distribution of the stresses locally at that region, but not globally

Figure 1421

Same, the local factor could be the reason behind the highest value which is higher than that of the tapered featureless

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Figure 1355

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Slice: Stored energy density (N/m^2)

Figure 1356

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The concept of more flexible total hip arthroplasty that ensued more stress more successes and keep the bone away from stress shielding is well approved and known rule. Multiple disciplines that are dealing with different types of intraosseous implanted devices must follow the same rule in every other discipline wherever they are correct. The concept of orthopedic surgery that had been approved on a scientific basis must dislodge supposed imaginary concepts in dental implantology without any objections. The neglect of this fact in implant dentistry will lead to a vicious circle in the wrong explanation of many failures we are facing and the wrong conclusion based upon these concepts, which make the patients are the only receivers by the resultant insults. Many implantology concepts are speculative and empirical and in many cases, we depend upon the compensating ability of the body to withstand the continuous insult by a poor performance of the poorly designed implant.

Addition of threats to the core had not changed the strain regions significantly but rather it called cause addition of strains to the thread regions

Figure 1106

Figure 1107

Very close to figure 34

Slice: Second principal stress (N/m²) Slice: First principal stress (N/m²) Slice: Third principal stress (N/m²)

Figure 1108

Close to figure 33

Slice: Second principal strain (1)

Figure 1109

Close to figure 36

Figure 1110

Same as figure 37

As other criteria fail to demonstrate significant difference between core and the threaded basal implants models, that means there more second principal strain at the threaded basal implant is due to local effect of bending of threads at their bases

Figure 1111

Displacement is much greater than the thin tapered featureless model

The addition of threads add a slight increase to the stiffness

Figure 1112

Stress is less than the in the threaded basal implant due to stiffer threaded basal

Figure 1113

Figure 1114

Positive volumetric strain here is lower than the threaded basal implant but the compression is the same

Figure 1125

Figure 1126

Figure 1127

Figure 1128

Figure 1129

Figure 1130

Figure 1131

Figure 1132

Figure 1133

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Author profile

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